

THE HISTORY OF THE CREATION OF UZBEK FOLK INSTRUMENTS AND THE RAVINES OF IMPROVEMENT

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Annotation: This article explores the role of Uzbek folk instruments in the musical art of the ancestral age and the processes of improvement to the present day.

Key words: Abu Nasr Farabi, Al-Khwarazmi, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Safiuddin Urmawi, Abdurahman Jomiy, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, music, instrument.

Considered an invaluable asset of the Uzbek people-national our musical instruments have their uniqueness, the decoration of the pattern special in our national musical culture with its attractiveness, the variety of sound freshness and the incomparable possibilities of performance holds the seat. Musical instruments azal-long ago Uzbek people daily life, becoming important in his spiritual life closely connected with the style. They are still today people have their own characteristics in the formation of their worldview. Especially the art of Instrumental Performance our ancestors formed by centuries as a unique aesthetic tool, not only in the science of music, but also in the creation of modern music it has also been of great interest. All his own the study of features and edges, on the other hand, helps to enrich the practice of Instrumental Performance. Uzbek folk National Instruments have a huge musical heritage, these instruments are the material, spiritual and cultural wealth of our people. Uzbek folk instruments underwent many refinements before modern performance reached the level of demand. Instrument performance and instrument refinement have continued from ancient times to the present. Examples of this include Abu Nasr Farabi's "Great Book of music", Abu Ali Ibn Sina's "Book of healing", Al-Khwarazmi's "Book

of knowledge”, Safiuddin Urmawi's “book of supremacy”, Abdurahman Jami's “treatise on music”, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's “Baburnoma”, which recorded instrumental performance as well as necessary sources on our National Instruments. Our national instruments were only adapted to perform in a room setting, and their performance on stage was weakly in terms of touch. Later in the early 20th century, our instruments were further refined in modern demand by hofiz Shorahim Shoumarov, lyricist Matyusuf Kharratov, Master Usman Zufarov, Master Rozimatkhan Isaboyev. By Shorahim Shoumarov, there are different types of percussion instruments made of different materials, of which the most afzali as well as the khijjak, made of wood, were considered to be the intended instrument. The Matyusuf Kharratov range expands the range of the instrument at the expense of adding additional strings to the Changer, which is small and has a diatonic reverberator. Later Master Rozimatkhan Isaboyev also made himself a dust instrument in 1902, inspired by Ramazonokhun's performance on the dust instrument from Kashgar, and wore a string of feathers to make the sound sound louder. Master Uthman Zufarov, on the other hand, made several types of tanbur, dutor, and rubob. Master Uthman Zufarov was one of the first to make low-register instruments for the ensemble community, namely, the large dutor, the large tanbur, the large goosebumps, at the invitation of Yunus Rajabi. They were performed by instrumentalists in an ensemble led by Yunus Rajabi.

In 1934, V. At the experimental laboratory, which improves special instruments at the Institute of scientific research of art studies, opened at the suggestion of Uspensky, master Usman Zufarov conducts activities with several of his students. Formed in 1936 under the direction of Tokasin Jalilov, the unison orchestra, consisting of 98 musicians, includes a large tanbur made by master Uthman Zufarov, a large Thunderbolt, and large dutors tested. At the first decadal of Uzbek art, held in Moscow in 1937, all the instruments made by Master Uthman Zufarov sounded on the theater stage.

Beginning in 1930, the idea of creating a family of instruments was put forward with the aim of forming multi-voice orchestras and ensembles. These were led by

Ashot Ivanovich Petrosyans. In this laboratory, A.I. Under the leadership of Petrosyans S. Didenko, V. Romanchenko, A. Kevhoyans, X. Mukhitdinov, A. Abdugofurov, A. Tarasov, V. Shitikov, N. Ryukhin, M. Turdiyev, F. Musical instrument masters such as Bortnik conducted instrument modernization. In addition to the creation of the family of instruments, the introduction of 12-stage equal-tempered chromatic vocalizers into string-clicking instruments as well as the first experimental work on a chromatic dust instrument were carried out.

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